

REY COMPLEX FIGURE TEST (NEUROPSI)

Name and Surname:

1. Cross in the upper-left corner, outside the rectangle: **Copy:** **Recall:**
2. Large rectangle: **Copy:** **Recall:**
3. Diagonal cross: **Copy:** **Recall:**
4. Horizontal midline inside unit 2: **Copy:** **Recall:**
5. Vertical midline inside unit 2: **Copy:** **Recall:**
6. Small rectangle on the left side of unit 2: **Copy:** **Recall:**
7. Small segment placed above unit 6: **Copy:** **Recall:**
8. Four parallel lines on the side: **Copy:** **Recall:**
upper left of unit 2: **Copy:** **Recall:**
9. Triangle above the upper-right side of unit 2: **Copy:** **Recall:**
10. Small vertical line inside unit 2, **Copy:** **Recall:**
below unit 9: **Copy:** **Recall:**
11. Circle with three dots inside unit 2: **Copy:** **Recall:**
12. Five parallel lines inside unit 2: **Copy:** **Recall:**
crossing unit 3 at the lower-right side: **Copy:** **Recall:**
13. Sides of the triangle attached to unit 2 on the right: **Copy:** **Recall:**
14. Diamond attached to unit 13: **Copy:** **Recall:**
15. Vertical line inside unit 13, parallel to the right side of unit 2: **Copy:** **Recall:**
16. Horizontal line inside unit 13, continuing from unit 4 to the right: **Copy:** **Recall:**
17. Cross attached to unit 5, below unit 2: **Copy:** **Recall:**
18. Square attached to unit 2 at the lower-left side: **Copy:** **Recall:**

TOTAL COPY:

TOTAL RECALL:

Each of the 18 parts of the figure is evaluated and assigned the following score:

0 — Unit is absent or unrecognizable.

0.5 — Unit is recognizable but distorted or incomplete, and placed in the wrong position.

1 — Unit is correctly drawn but placed in the wrong position; or correctly placed but distorted or incomplete.

2 — Unit is correctly drawn and placed in the correct position as shown in the model.

Maximum possible score: 36 points.